

COHESION, INTEGRATION AND SECURITIZATION CHALLENGES FOR EU MIGRATION LAW AND POLICY

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Abstract. *Migration is a social phenomenon of human moves dating back to early civilizations and continuing even in recent times. People all over the world migrate due to various reasons. The European Union is not an exception in this concert of migrations. Migration in the European Union represents a very complex and stuffy topic for theorists and practitioners.*

Keywords: *migration, minority, law, community, EU*

Preliminaries. Migration is a social phenomenon of human moves dating back to early civilizations and continuing even in recent times. People all over the world migrate due to various reasons. The European Union is not an exception in this concert of migrations. Migration in the European Union represents a very complex and stuffy topic for theorists and practitioners.

As migration comprises emigration and immigration facets, this research focuses primarily on immigration, because since the foundation of European Communities it became a social and institutional problem of united Europe. Specific provisions on immigration are to be identified in the primary, secondary and supplementary sources of European Union law.

In the same time migration – emigration and immigration – is an object of study for various disciplines: law, political science, economics, international relations, sociology, anthropology, demography, geography, history, etc. Migration theories across the disciplines would serve in performing interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary research approaches of this social phenomenon.

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Migration theories across disciplines

Discipline	Research question(s)	Levels / units of analysis	Dominant theories	Sample hypothesis
Anthropology	How does migration effect cultural change and effect ethnic identity?	More micro / individuals households, groups	Relational or structuralist and transnational Theories of migration (cost/ benefit and structural; theories in integration (assimilation and pluralist- based); theories of migration effects (economic, social structural, and cultural)	Social networks help maintain cultural difference
Demography	To what extent do immigrant and native populations become more similar over time?	Individuals, immigrant groups, ethno-racial groups, national foreign-born populations	Rationalist: cost-benefit and utility maximizing behavior	Immigrants will not become successfully integrated when they experience significant membership exclusion
Economics	What explains the propensity to migrate and its effects?	Micro/individuals	Rationalist: cost-benefit and utility maximizing behavior	Incorporation varies with the level of human capital of immigrants
Geography	What explains the socio-spatial patterns of migration? How has a phenomenon (e.g. causes, structures, processes, consequences of migration) or a relationship (e.g. gender and migration) changed or persisted over time?	Macro, meso and micro/individuals, households and groups	Relational, structural, and transnational	Incorporation depends on ethnic networks and residential patterns
History	What explains the propensity to migrate and its effects?	Varies temporally (from short- to medium and long- term) as well as spatially	Periodization	Usually not applicable
Law	How does the law influence migration?	Macro and micro/the political and legal system	Institutionalist and rationalist (borrows from all the social sciences)	Rights create incentive structures for migration and incorporation
Political science	Why do states have difficulty controlling migration?	More macro/political and international systems	Institutionalist and rationalist	States are often captured by pro-immigrant interests
Sociology	What explains incorporation and exclusion?	Macro/ethnic groups and social class	Structuralist or institutionalist	Incorporation varies with social and human capital

Source: C. Brettell, J. Hollifield. *Migration Theory: Talking across Disciplines*. p.4

Usually research on this topic is done separately by each science (J. Arango, C. Brettell, J. Hollifield, G. Hugo, A. Kouaouci, D. Massey, A. Pellegrino, A. Portes, A. Singleton, E. Taylor, S. Vetovec). Interdisciplinary approaches are in progress. This research would embrace rather an interdisciplinary focus to analyze cohesion, integration and securitization matters on immigration within the thematic law and policy of the European Union.

Research objectives of the phenomenon of immigration in the European Union comprise three layers: cohesion, integration and securitization.

These issues are crucial for both the European Union and Member States in the light of the European Union law and policy in this field. Provisional elements on immigration matters such as rationale, premises, motives, causes and effects, seem to be of great importance, both inside and outside the European Union, to tackle on this phenomenon. For instance, throughout its history Europe has been considered as the “Old Continent”, the cradle of civilization, the land of prosperity, and, for the last sixty year period, the land of peace. This should be taken into consideration when discussing the phenomenon of immigration in the European Union. C. Bonifazi, M. Okólski, J. Schoorl and P. Simon underline that “the Southern European countries have emerged as centres of attraction and have become the new promised land for migrants coming from both old and new sending countries. In turn, the Western European countries have been looking for a new type of immigrant – better educated and possessing skills that can be adapted to modern and fast-developing technologies. At the same time, these countries have suddenly been confronted with integrating the children of immigrants recruited for employment in the first 25 years after the end of World War II. The result has been a radical transformation of all the aspects related directly and indirectly to migration dynamics, including the direction and size of migration flows, migration policies, the role of various countries in the continental migration panorama, and the rising concerns for integration processes both at the policy and scientific levels”¹. EU attractiveness for immigrants is determined by foundation grounding of united Europe, on the one hand. On the other hand, the European Union is becoming more involved in this field as a result of continental and international migration.

¹ C. Bonifazi, M. Okólski, J. Schoorl, P. Simon. *International Migration in Europe: New Trends and New Methods of Analysis*, p. 9.

According to B. Rechel, Ph. Mladovsky, W. Devillé, B. Rijks, R. Petrova-Benedict, M. McKee, migration influences the health of Member States, being a key issue for health-policy making in the European Union.

The cartoons are very relevant in this respect. Additionally, for several Member States immigration became a sort of business by facilitating financial influxes to develop national economies with outside capitals.

Ultimately, immigration is a versatile institutional, social and security issue of Member States and the European Union as well. Member States have no sufficient capabilities to settle separately the question of immigration nor can the European Union, because of granted competences by founding treaties.

EU legal provisions on migration. As the phenomenon of migration has been affecting more and more the European Union, legal regulations come to face this issue. It is worth considering to what extent the European Union law can influence migration.

The Treaty on European Union contains an article on immigration. Article 3 (ex Article 2 TEU) states: “(2) The Union shall offer its citizens an area of freedom, security and justice without internal frontiers, in which the free movement of persons is ensured in conjunction with appropriate measures with respect to external border controls, asylum, immigration and the prevention and combating of crime”². The immigration issue is mentioned among the provisions on the aims of the European Union.

The Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union includes provisions on migration in the title V: Area of Freedom, Security and Justice, chapter 4: Policies on border checks, asylum and immigration alongside with provisions on free movement of persons.

Free movement of persons, services and capital of the title IV, refers in chapter 1 to workers. Article 45 (ex Article 39 TEC) guarantees that “1. Freedom of movement for workers shall be secured within the Union. 2. Such freedom of movement shall entail the abolition of any discrimination based on nationality between workers of the Member States as regards employment, remuneration and other conditions of work and employment. 3. It shall entail the right, subject to limitations justified on grounds of public policy, public security or public health: (a) to accept offers of employment actually made; (b) to move freely within the territory of Member States for this purpose; (c) to stay in a Member State for the purpose of employment in accordance with the provisions governing the employment of nationals of that State laid down by law, regulation or administrative action; (d) to remain in the territory of a Member State after having been employed in that State,

² *Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union*, p. 17.

subject to conditions which shall be embodied in regulations to be drawn up by the Commission”³. There is a close linkage between the free movement of persons and migration, because the movement of persons is not possible outside migration practices.

Corroborated with Article 45 (ex Article 39 TEC), Article 48 (ex Article 42 TEC) underline that “the European Parliament and the Council shall, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure, adopt such measures in the field of social security as are necessary to provide freedom of movement for workers; to this end, they shall make arrangements to secure for employed and self- employed migrant workers and their dependants: (a) aggregation, for the purpose of acquiring and retaining the right to benefit and of calculating the amount of benefit, of all periods taken into account under the laws of the several countries; (b) payment of benefits to persons resident in the territories of Member States”⁴. The European Union law comes with guarantees for the free movement of persons.

Article 67 (ex Article 61 TEC and ex Article 29 TEU) reads that the “1. The Union shall constitute an area of freedom, security and justice with respect for fundamental rights and the different legal systems and traditions of the Member States. 2. It shall ensure the absence of internal border controls for persons and shall frame a common policy on asylum, immigration and external border control, based on solidarity between Member States, which is fair towards third-country nationals. For the purpose of this Title, stateless persons shall be treated as third-country nationals”⁵. The area of freedom, security and justice shapes the platform for the European policy on migration.

Article 79 (ex Article 63, points 3 and 4, TEC) says that the “1. The Union shall develop a common immigration policy aimed at ensuring, at all stages, the efficient management of migration flows, fair treatment of third-country nationals residing legally in Member States, and the prevention of, and enhanced measures to combat, illegal immigration and trafficking in human beings. 2. For the purposes of paragraph 1, the European Parliament and the Council, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure, shall adopt measures in the following areas: (a) the conditions of entry and residence, and standards on the issue by Member States of long-term visas and residence permits, including those for the purpose of family reunification; (b) the definition of the rights of third-country nationals residing legally in a Member State, including the conditions governing freedom of movement and of residence in other Member States; (c) illegal immigration and unauthorised residence,

³ *Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, p. 65-66.

⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 67.

⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 73.

including removal and repatriation of persons residing without authorization; (d) combating trafficking in persons, in particular women and children. 3. The Union may conclude agreements with third countries for the readmission to their countries of origin or provenance of third-country nationals who do not or who no longer fulfill the conditions for entry, presence or residence in the territory of one of the Member States”⁶. The European migration policy is followed by agreements with third countries.

The Protocol No 7 *On the Privileges and Immunities of the European Union* includes reference to officials and servants of the European Union in chapter V. Article 11 (ex Article 12) emphasize that “in the territory of each Member State and whatever their nationality, officials and other servants of the Union shall: (a) subject to the provisions of the Treaties relating, on the one hand, to the rules on the liability of officials and other servants towards the Union and, on the other hand, to the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice of the European Union in disputes between the Union and its officials and other servants, be immune from legal proceedings in respect of acts performed by them in their official capacity, including their words spoken or written. They shall continue to enjoy this immunity after they have ceased to hold office; (b) together with their spouses and dependent members of their families, not be subject to immigration restrictions or to formalities for the registration of aliens”⁷. The European officials and servants are protected by the European Union law.

Primary law of the European Union concerning migration contains provisions on access to the territory, procedures, visa policy, status, associated documentation, cooperation with third countries and references to officials and servants. The provisions to a certain extent are restrictive measures against migration.

Secondary law on migration retains two highly relevant EU Council Directives enacted in 2003. These directives set expressly the framework for migrants’ status in EU Member States: Directive 2003/109/EC concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents, and Directive 2003/86/EC on the right to family reunification.

It is worth mentioning that the free movement of persons is a fundamental right in the European Union law. The free movement of EU citizens is materialized through the area of freedom, security and justice. In other words it is an area without internal borders. Lifting internal borders challenged management of external borders, entry and residence of third-country nationals.

⁶ Ibidem, p.77.

⁷ Protocol No 7 *On the Privileges and Immunities of the European Union*, p. 269.

The free movement of persons has provisions in the Schengen Agreement (1985) and the Schengen Convention (1990), being abolished border controls between participants.

All these initiatives created legal provisions, which regulate migration inside the European Union and immigration of non-EU nationals. The secondary legislation on migration comprises the following aspects: free movement of Member States nationals within the European Union, Schengen information system, external borders, visas, asylum, rights of non-EU nationals, and agreements with third countries.

Legal provisions on free movement of Member States nationals inside the European Union are included in the following acts: Directive 2004/38/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the right of citizens of the Union and their family members to move and reside freely within the territory of the Member States amending Regulation (EEC) No 1612/68 and repealing Directives 64/221/EEC, 68/360/EEC, 72/194/EEC, 73/148/EEC, 75/34/EEC, 75/35/EEC, 90/364/EEC, 90/365/EEC and 93/96/EEC; 1999/307/EC: Council Decision of 1 May 1999 laying down the detailed arrangements for the integration of the Schengen Secretariat into the General Secretariat of the Council; 1999/436/EC: Council Decision of 20 May 1999 determining, in conformity with the relevant provisions of the Treaty establishing the European Community and the Treaty on European Union, the legal basis for each of the provisions or decisions which constitute the Schengen acquis; 1999/435/EC: Council Decision of 20 May 1999 concerning the definition of the Schengen acquis for the purpose of determining, in conformity with the relevant provisions of the Treaty establishing the European Community and the Treaty on European Union, the legal basis for each of the provisions or decisions which constitute the acquis; Regulation (EC) No 562/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2006 establishing a Community Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code); Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 16 September 2011 – Schengen governance – strengthening the area without internal border control; The Stockholm Programme – An open and secure Europe serving and protecting citizens; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 20 April 2010 – Delivering an area of freedom, security and justice for Europe's citizens – Action Plan Implementing the Stockholm Programme. The great number of acts concerning the free movement of persons speaks about the importance of this right among other European rights.

Specific provisions on Schengen information system appear in the following acts of the European Union: Council Regulation (EC) No 1104/2008 of 24 October 2008 on migration from the Schengen Information System (SIS 1+) to the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II); Council Decision 2008/839/JHA of 24 October 2008 on migration from the Schengen Information System (SIS 1+) to the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II); Regulation (EC) No 1987/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on the establishment, operation and use of the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II); Council Decision 2007/533/JHA of 12 June 2007 on the establishment, operation and use of the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II); Regulation (EC) No 1986/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 regarding access to the Second Generation Schengen Information System (SIS II) by the services in the Member States responsible for issuing vehicle registration certificates; Communication from the Commission - Legislative package establishing an Agency for the operational management of large-scale IT systems in the area of freedom, security and justice COM(2009) 293, COM(2009) 294, SEC (2009) 836, SEC (2009) 837; Council Regulation (EC) No 871/2004 of 29 April 2004 concerning the introduction of some new functions for the Schengen Information System, including in the fight against terrorism; Council Decision 2005/211/JHA of 24 February 2005 concerning the introduction of some new functions for the Schengen Information System, including in the fight against terrorism; Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on improved effectiveness, enhanced interoperability and synergies among European databases in the area of Justice and Home Affairs COM/2005/0597.

Provisions on external borders of the European Union make the object in the following European acts: Regulation (EC) No 1931/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 laying down rules on local border traffic at the external land borders of the Member States and amending the provisions of the Schengen Convention; Council Regulation (EC) No 2007/2004 of 26 October 2004 establishing a European Agency for the Management of Operational Cooperation at the External Borders of the Member States of the European Union; Regulation (EC) No 863/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 establishing a mechanism for the creation of Rapid Border Intervention Teams and amending Council Regulation (EC) No 2007/2004 as regards that mechanism and regulating the tasks and powers of guest officers; Decision No 574/2007/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 May 2007 establishing the External Borders Fund for the period 2007 to 2013 as part of the General programme Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows; Council Directive 2004/82/EC of 29 April 2004 on

the obligation of carriers to communicate passenger data; 2010/131/: Council Decision of 25 February 2010 on setting up the Standing Committee on operational cooperation on internal security; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: The EU Internal Security Strategy in Action: Five steps towards a more secure Europe COM/2010/0673; Communication of 13 February 2008 from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Preparing the next steps in border management in the European Union; Communication of 13 February 2008 from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Examining the creation of a European border surveillance system (EUROSUR); Communication from the Commission to the Council – Reinforcing the management of the European Union's Southern Maritime Borders COM/2006/0733.

Specific provisions on visas when travelling in the European Union are in three categories of European acts: (1) visa policy – Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a Community Code on Visas (Visa Code); Council Regulation (EC) No 539/2001 of 15 March 2001 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement; Council Regulation (EC) No 1683/95 of 29 May 1995 laying down a uniform format for visas; Council Regulation (EC) No 693/2003 of 14 April 2003 establishing a specific Facilitated Transit Document (FTD), a Facilitated Rail Transit Document (FRTD) and amending the Common Consular Instructions and the Common Manual; Corrigendum to Council Regulation (EC) No 1295/2003 of 15 July 2003 relating to measures envisaged to facilitate the procedures for applying for and issuing visas for members of the Olympic family taking part in the 2004 Olympic or Paralympic Games in Athens; Joint action 96/197/JAI, of 4 March 1996 adopted by the Council on the basis of Article K.3 of the Treaty on European Union on airport transit arrangements; (2) information system on visas – Regulation (EC) No 767/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 July 2008 concerning the Visa Information System (VIS) and the exchange of data between Member States on short-stay visas (VIS Regulation); 2004/512/EC: 2004/512/EC: Council Decision of 8 June 2004 establishing the Visa Information System (VIS); Council Decision 2008/633/JHA of 23 June 2008 concerning access for consultation of the Visa Information System (VIS) by designated authorities of Member States and by Europol for the purposes of the prevention, detection and investigation of terrorist offences and of other serious criminal offences; (3) consular cooperation and document fraud – Council Regulation (EC) No 2252/2004 of 13 December 2004 on

standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States; Council Decision of 27 March 2000 on the improved exchange of information to combat counterfeit travel documents; Joint Action 98/700/JHA of 3 December 1998 adopted by the Council on the basis of Article K.3 of the Treaty on European Union concerning the setting up of a European Image-Archiving System (FADO); Council Recommendation 98/C 189/02 of 28 May 1998 on the provision of forgery detection equipment at ports of entry to the European Union; Council Recommendation 99/C 140/01 of 29 April 1999 on the provision for the detection of false or falsified documents in the visa departments of representations abroad and in the offices of domestic authorities dealing with the issue or extension of visas; Council recommendation of 4 March 1996 relating to local consular cooperation regarding visas.

Provisions on asylum in the European Union are worked out in the following types of European acts such as: (1) European asylum system – Regulation (EU) No 439/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 establishing a European Asylum Support Office; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council of 2 September 2009 on the establishment of a joint EU resettlement programme COM(2009) 447; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 17 June 2008 – Policy Plan on Asylum: An integrated approach to protection across the EU COM(2008) 360; Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament of 4 June 2004 on the managed entry in the EU of persons in need of international protection and the enhancement of the protection capacity of the regions of origin: “improving access to durable solutions” COM(2004)410; Green Paper of 6 June 2007 on the future common European asylum system COM (2007) 301; (2) minimal harmonisation of national legislation – Council Directive 2005/85/EC of 1 December 2005 on minimum standards on procedures in Member States for granting and withdrawing refugee status; Council Directive 2004/83/EC of 29 April 2004 on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons as refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection and the content of the protection granted; Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers; Council Resolution of 20 June 1995 on minimum guarantees for asylum procedures, Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof; (3) cooperation and

coordination of asylum systems – Council Regulation (EC) No 343/2003 of 18 February 2003 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an asylum application lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national; Council Regulation (EC) No 2725/2000 of 11 December 2000 concerning the establishment of ‘Eurodac’ for the comparison of fingerprints for the effective application of the Dublin Convention; Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on strengthened practical cooperation - New structures, new approaches: improving the quality of decision making in the common European asylum system COM(2006) 67; (4) financial programmes – Decision No 573/2007/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 May 2007 establishing the European Refugee Fund for the period 2008 to 2013 as part of the General programme Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows and repealing Council Decision 2004/904/EC.

Provisions on immigration and rights of non-EU nationals in the European Union are set in the following types of acts: (1) immigration policy – Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 4 May 2011 - Communication on migration COM(2011) 24; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 17 June 2008 – A Common Immigration Policy for Europe: Principles, actions and tools COM(2008) 35; Communication from the Commission on a policy plan on legal migration COM (2005) 669; Commission Staff Working Document of 8 October 2008 – Strengthening actions and tools to meet integration challenges – Report to the 2008 Ministerial Conference on Integration SEC (2008) 2626; Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 1 September 2005 – A Common Agenda for Integration – Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union COM (2005) 389; (2) entry and residence – Council Regulation (EC) No 1030/2002 of 13 June 2002 laying down a uniform format for residence permits for third-country nationals; Council Directive 2005/71/EC of 12 October 2005 on a specific procedure for admitting third-country nationals for the purposes of scientific research; Council Directive 2009/50/EC of 25 May 2009 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment; Council Directive 2004/114/EC of 13 December 2004 on the conditions of admission of third-country nationals for the purposes of studies, pupil exchange, unremunerated training or voluntary service; Council Directive 2004/81/EC of 29 April 2004 on the residence permit issued to third-country

nationals who are victims of trafficking in human beings or who have been the subject of an action to facilitate illegal immigration, who cooperate with the competent authorities; Council Directive 2003/109/EC of 25 November 2003 concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents; Council Directive 2003/86/EC of 22 September 2003 on the right to family reunification; Proposal of 23 October 2007 for a Council Directive on a single application procedure for a single permit for Non-EU Member Country nationals to reside and work in the territory of a Member State and on a common set of rights for Non-EU Member Country workers legally residing in a Member State; Council resolution of 30 November 1994 relating to the limitations on the admission of third-country nationals for the purpose of pursuing activities as self-employed persons; Council Resolution of 20 June 1994 on limitation on admission of third-country nationals to the territory of the Member States for employment; (3) illegal immigration – Council Directive 2002/90/EC of 28 November 2002 defining the facilitation of unauthorised entry, transit and residence; 2002/946/JHA: Council framework Decision of 28 November 2002 on the strengthening of the penal framework to prevent the facilitation of unauthorised entry, transit and residence; Directive 2009/52/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2009 providing for minimum standards on sanctions and measures against employers of illegally staying third-country nationals; Council Directive 2001/51/EC of 28 June 2001 supplementing the provisions of Article 26 of the Convention implementing the Schengen Agreement of 14 June 1985; Council Regulation (EC) No 377/2004 of 19 February 2004 on the creation of an immigration liaison officers network; 2006/616/EC: Council Decision of 24 July 2006 on the conclusion, on behalf of the European Community, of the Protocol Against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air, supplementing the United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organised Crime concerning the provisions of the Protocol, in so far as the provisions of this Protocol fall within the scope of Articles 179 and 181a of the Treaty establishing the European Community; 2006/617/EC: Council Decision of 24 July 2006 on the conclusion, on behalf of the European Community, of the Protocol Against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air, supplementing the United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organised Crime concerning the provisions of the Protocol, in so far as the provisions of the Protocol fall within the scope of Part III, Title IV of the Treaty establishing the European Community; Communication from the Commission of 19 July 2006 on policy priorities in the fight against illegal immigration of third-country nationals COM(2006) 402; Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 4 June 2004 - Study on the links between legal

and illegal migration COM(2004) 412; (4) return and expulsion – Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals; Council Directive 2001/40/EC of 28 May 2001 on the mutual recognition of decisions on the expulsion of third country nationals; 2004/573/EC: Council Decision of 29 April 2004 on the organisation of joint flights for removals from the territory of two or more Member States, of third-country nationals who are subjects of individual removal orders; (5) information and cooperation – Regulation (EC) No 862/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on Community statistics on migration and international protection and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 311/76 on the compilation of statistics on foreign workers; Council Regulation (EEC) No 311/76 of 9 February 1976 on the compilation of statistics on foreign workers; 2008/381/EC: Council Decision of 14 May 2008 establishing a European Migration Network; 2006/688/EC: Council Decision of 5 October 2006 on the establishment of a mutual information mechanism concerning Member States' measures in the areas of asylum and immigration; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council of 20 July 2010 – Overview of information management in the area of freedom, security and justice COM(2010) 385; (6) financial programmes – 2007/435/EC: Council Decision of 25 June 2007 establishing the European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals for the period 2007 to 2013 as part of the General programme Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows; Decision No 575/2007/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 May 2007 establishing the European Return Fund for the period 2008 to 2013 as part of the General Programme Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows; Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament establishing a framework programme on solidarity and management of migration flows for the period 2007-2013 COM(2005) 123.

Provisions on relations between the European Union with third countries are included in the following types of acts: (1) general provisions – Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 8 October 2008 – Strengthening the Global Approach to Migration: Increasing coordination, coherence and synergies COM(2008) 611; Communication from the Commission of 16 May 2007 to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions applying the Global Approach to Migration to the Eastern and South-Eastern Regions Neighbouring the European Union COM(2007) 247; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the

Regions of 16 May 2007 on circular migration and mobility partnerships between the European Union and third countries COM(2007) 248; Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament – The global approach to migration one year on: towards a comprehensive European migration policy COM(2006) 735; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council – Thematic programme for the cooperation with Non-EU Member Countries in the areas of migration and asylum COM(2006) 26; Commission Communication to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 1 September 2005 -Migration and Development: some concrete orientations COM(2005) 390; Commission Communication of 3.12.2002 to the Council and European Parliament: Integrating migration issues in the European Union's relations with third countries COM (2002) 703; (2) external borders and visas – 2007/821/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Albania on the facilitation of the issuance of visas; 2007/822/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and Bosnia and Herzegovina on the facilitation of the issuance of visas; 2007/823/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Montenegro on the facilitation of the issuance of visas; 2007/824/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia on the facilitation of the issuance of visas; 2007/825/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Serbia on the facilitation of the issuance of visas; 2007/340/EC: Council Decision of 19 April 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Russian Federation on the facilitation of issuance of short-stay visas; Communication from the Commission to the Council of 18 September 2002 – Kaliningrad: Transit COM (2002) 510; (3) asylum – Commission Communication to the Council and the European Parliament of 1 September 2005 on regional protection programmes COM(2005) 388; (4) return and readmission – 2004/424/EC: Council Decision of 21 April 2004 concerning the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Macao Special Administrative Region of the People's Republic of China on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2004/80/EC: Council Decision of 17 December 2003 concerning the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region of the People's Republic of China on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2010/649/EU: Council Decision of 7 October 2010 on

the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Islamic Republic of Pakistan on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2007/826/EC: Council Decision of 22 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Moldova on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2007/839/EC: Council Decision of 29 November 2007 concerning the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and Ukraine on readmission of persons; 2011/118/EU: Council Decision of 18 January 2011 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Union and Georgia on the readmission of persons residing without authorization, 2007/341/EC: Council Decision of 19 April 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Russian Federation on readmission; 2005/809/EC: Council Decision of 7 November 2005 concerning the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Albania on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2007/817/EC: Council Decision of 8 November 2007 on the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; 2005/372/EC: Council Decision of 3 March 2005 concerning the conclusion of the Agreement between the European Community and the Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka on the readmission of persons residing without authorisation.

It can be easily noticed that the exhaustive legislation of the European Union regulates all spheres related to migration either of EU nationals or non-EU nationals. A very developed and sophisticated legislation is a guarantee for better management of migration phenomenon.

Migration Policy / Policies. The field of migration is a national competence of Member States. But according to Article 4 and Article 6 of the *Treaty on Functioning of the European Union*, they enable the European Union to take necessary measures to shape the migration policy at the supra-level. The European Union's migration policy on common principles seems to take form in the past years.

Migration policy addresses all forms of mobility to, from and through a Member State's territory. It encompasses policy towards foreign nationals, as well as policy towards a Member State's own citizens, covering various areas: immigration policy, integration policy, and emigration policy.

The migration policy of the European Union deals with both regular and irregular migration issues. The most relevant acts on migration policy can be mentioned the following ones: Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 1 September 2005 – A Common Agenda for Integration

– Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union COM(2005) 389; Communication from the Commission on a policy plan on legal migration COM (2005) 669; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 5 December 2007 – “Towards a Common Immigration Policy” COM(2007) 780; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 17 June 2008 – A Common Immigration Policy for Europe: Principles, actions and tools COM(2008) 359; European Pact on Immigration and Asylum of 24 September 2008; Commission Staff Working Document of 8 October 2008 – Strengthening actions and tools to meet integration challenges – Report to the 2008 Ministerial Conference on Integration SEC(2008) 2626; Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 4 May 2011 – Communication on migration COM(2011) 248.

Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 1 September 2005 – A Common Agenda for Integration – Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union COM(2005) 389 establishes common basic principles for a coherent EU level approach towards integrating third-country nationals in the democratic society of the European Union.

Communication from the Commission on a policy plan on legal migration COM (2005) 669 proposes measures on labour immigration for highly skilled workers, seasonal workers, intra-corporate transferees (ICTs) and remunerated trainees.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 5 December 2007 – “Towards a Common Immigration Policy” COM(2007) 780 strives to encourage Member States and European institutions to work in partnership and transparency; define common principles and rules regarding coherence and solidarity; implement existing EU strategies and policies (anti-discrimination policies, employment strategy, open method of coordination on social inclusion, social protection and health care); provide quantifiable indicators for evaluating the impact of measures adopted; improve cooperation between national administrations.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 17 June 2008 – A Common Immigration Policy for Europe: Principles, actions and tools COM(2008) 359 focuses on three key concepts: prosperity – the

contribution of legal immigration to the socio-economic development of the European Union; clear rules and a level playing field; matching skills and need, and integration to successful immigration; solidarity – coordination between EU countries and cooperation with non-EU countries; transparency, trust and cooperation; efficient and coherent use of available means; partnership with non-EU countries; security – effective fight against illegal immigration; a visa policy in serving the interests of Europe and its partners; integrated border management; stepping up the fight against illegal immigration and zero tolerance for trafficking in human beings; effective and sustainable return policies.

European Pact on Immigration and Asylum of 24 September 2008 refers to organising legal immigration, controlling irregular immigration, improving border controls, creating a Europe of asylum, collaborating with countries of origin and transit.

Commission Staff Working Document of 8 October 2008 – Strengthening actions and tools to meet integration challenges – Report to the 2008 Ministerial Conference on Integration SEC(2008) 2626 engages a “dynamic two-way process of mutual accommodation”, the immigrants in the host societies, social alienation, common European modules for integration, monitoring and evaluation practices, employment, social inclusion and education.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 4 May 2011 – Communication on migration COM(2011) 248 addresses to crossing the borders, moving and living in the Schengen area, common European asylum system, and relations with third countries.

A great attention is paid to irregular migration: entry, residence, employment of non-EU migrants in without the necessary documents, permits or registration. The European Union has developed a policy framework for managing irregular migration. The Stockholm Programme contains the following priorities: to manage effectively and control the EU’s external borders; to combat human trafficking and smuggling; to encourage non-EU citizens who are not authorised to be in an EU country to leave voluntarily; to cooperate with migrants’ home countries and non-EU countries they pass through on their way to the European Union. EU protections for victims of human trafficking and EU rules on irregular migration represent a milestone of migration policy of the European Union.

Migration policy of the European Union has developed both from an internal and a diplomatic perspective, i.e. internal and cooperation challenges.

EU migration policy, an internal challenge. It is quite difficult to assert that there is a EU level framework on migration that could be compared to fully-fledged

national policies of Member States. It seems that the underdevelopment of a common migration policy is a direct consequence of the division of competences between the European Union and Member States.

Obstacles for cooperation on migration at European level. Due to the division of competences, the European Union has a limited ability to elaborate a sustainable migration policy. There are not excluded the existing tensions between the national and supranational views in the European Union regarding internal and international cooperation on migration. An explanation would be the diverging interests and priorities of Member States and the European Union, of sending and receiving countries. Another important issue could be, at this stage, the limited implementation capacities on migration of the European Union and Member States, as well as partner (sending) countries.

Push-pull factors causing migration in the European Union. When dealing with European migration more theories can be applied. But what is mostly affecting the European Union it is immigration and the problems which emerge in the consequence. In this respect it is valuable to make use of the historical-structural theory of Lee push-pull factors, characterizing immigration in the European Union.

Among the push factors that force people to go in the countries of the European Union are few opportunities for individuals, lack of or not enough jobs, inadequate living or / and working conditions, famine or drought, political fear or persecution, death threats, slavery or forced labour in the country of origin, poor medical care, loss of wealth, natural disasters, poor housing, landlord / tenant issues, bullying, discrimination, desire for more political or religious freedom, poor chances of marrying, condemned housing, war, etc. Of course, this is not an exhaustive or limitative list of push factors influencing emigration in the European Union for third-country nationals. Other push factors can be identified individually in each case of immigration.

On the other hand, among the pull factors applicable for immigration in the European Union can be mentioned better job opportunities, better living conditions, more political and / or religious freedom, enjoyment, better education, better medical care, better security, family links, industry, better chances of marrying. In this case, the factors are not exhaustive or limitative to. These factors appear in the course of integration of European countries.

After a brief review of push-pull migration factors it is worth concluding that according to their nature they fall into the following types: social, political (including military), economic and religious. The forms of migration could be voluntary and involuntary.

Community cohesion of immigrants – a key relationship. Usually community cohesion remains linked to race equality, which is not quite sufficient. Certain questions can be formulated to reinforce community cohesion of immigrants. Is it possible a broader interaction within local community? Is it possible an integration of immigrants in the labour market? Is it possible to build good relations between settled communities and immigrants? Is conviviality possible in a new era of migration, an era of super-diversity (more groups, more countries of origin, with different ethnic identities, languages and religions)?

When considering community cohesion of immigrants it should be taken into consideration the greater variety of reasons for migration, the wider set of channels, the greater variety of legal status of immigrants, the issue of clustering predominantly in urban areas, the phenomenon of increasing globalization and, of course, the gaps in knowledge and understanding the situations and experiences of immigrants.

Integration of immigrants. The leading role in the process of integration of immigrants is and should be the European Union law as a guarantee to successful and beneficent influence of European legal provisions on migration. The European Union has already experienced managing and legislating on mobility and diversity. Integration policy measures of Member States are used to select those immigrants that are able and willing to integrate and deter those who are not (tests). Positioning of EU countries in relation to migration is extremely important in order to integrate effectively and efficiently the immigrating people.

Even integration of migrants is not the responsibility of the European Union, it supports Member States and non-EU nationals in the receiving countries. The “Common Basic Principles on Integration” (2004) and the “Common agenda for integration” (2005) seem to offer a benchmark for stakeholders and policymakers for integration of immigrants in the local communities of Member States: “The assumption that migration and integration should be strongly linked at the policy level is shared at the EU level and aims to influence member states. As a result, more and more national laws on migration and the legal status of third-country nationals relate the right to residency to some kind of integration proof. Integration is thus not only a sociological concept, it is more than ever a normative expectation of the majority population in multicultural societies towards the minorities⁸”.

Moreover the European Union has necessary instruments to support integration of immigrants:

- a network of national contact points on integration;
- the European Integration Forum (a platform for dialogue);
- the European webpage on integration;

⁸ C. Bonifazi, M. Okólski, J. Schoorl, P. Simon. *Op. Cit.*, p.10.

- a Handbook on integration;
- the European Integration Fund⁹.

Thus, the European Union in comparison with Member States has realized tangible steps towards improving the situation of immigrants and their better integration in the local communities, because they contribute to the economic, social and cultural development of the European Union.

Securitization of migration. The specific policy mediating belonging is the concept of securitization, which is supposed to deal with identification of existential threats. Member States identify migration as being one of the main factors weakening national tradition and societal homogeneity of European societies. Migration is perceived both an internal and external danger for the survival of national communities of Member States. As a consequence the securitization of migration is a natural structural effect of multiplicity of practices in this field.

Migration became a matter of EU security in the result of the spillover of the internal market into internal security. The effects produced a development of restrictive migration policy measures. Consequently, social construction of migration evolved into a security question, because of two major issues: immigrants are perceived as a challenge to the protection of national identity and welfare of Member States; and migration is seen as a danger to public order, cultural identity, domestic and labour market in Member States.

EU migration is characterized by a multiplicity of challenges such as economic and financial globalization, rise of poverty and deterioration of living conditions in non-EU countries, revival of racist and xenophobic parties and movements as well as rise of multiculturalism both inside and outside of the European Union.

Another facet of EU internal security is the cultural security. Immigrants challenge and revise the myth of national cultural homogeneity in Member States. As a result the national cultural identity is not constant, but variable. It is on the one hand. On the other hand the European integration process is highly involved in the development of and the struggle against the representation of migration as a cultural danger. The European integration process introduced the cultural significance of external border control and the limitation of free movement for third-country nationals. The European integration process promotes integration of the immigrants into the domestic societies of Member States in close relationship with the development of multicultural societies in an area of freedom, justice and common security.

The EC Report “Moving Europe: EU research on migration and policy needs” (2009) elaborated a couple of important tasks related to migration: networks of

⁹ See http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/immigration/integration/index_en.htm

excellence relevant to migration research; research projects on (statistics; citizenship issues; labour market and migration; gender and migration; environmental change and sustainable development; youth); the relevance of research results to policies (methodologies, terms and concepts; trans-nationalization and globalization; circular migration; well-managed immigration; illegal migration; under-documented/semi-documented migrants; dissemination of research results); the relationship between research, media and policy.

The acts speaks about and makes a plea for multiple stakeholders in dealing with migration, underlining the undeniable role of research and media in shaping the European migration policy, which is an inseparable part of EU internal security.

EU migration policy is the focus of the Stockholm Programme – an open and secure Europe serving and protecting citizens (2009). The act provides an open and secure Europe, serving and protecting EU citizens. At that stage it was a roadmap for developing the EU’s further migration policy. EU migration policy aims to build a Europe of “responsibility, solidarity and partnership in migration and asylum”¹⁰ with a “dynamic and comprehensive immigration policy”¹¹. The Stockholm Programme encourages coherence between migration policy and other closely related EU policy areas, such as development aid and relations with third countries.

Migration partnerships. Certain measures were taken in grounding legal cooperation on migration. These partnerships ought to take into consideration common actions inside the European Union, between Member States, and outside the European Union with third countries. The EU instrument with third countries is the “Global Approach to Migration and Mobility”. Seven mobility partnerships have been signed so far: with Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cape Verde, Georgia, Moldova, Morocco and Tunisia.

Migration-mobility shift. Although we still use the notion of migration, there are approaches inclining to consider a shift from migration to mobility of people in a world of globalization processes.

Traditional theories of migration – of movement by people from one place to another with the intention of settling in the new location, external migration vs. internal migration, emigration vs. immigration – do not fit with the new realities, the challenged human condition and the individual fulfillment of individuals in recent times. Hein de Haas offers an alternative theory, a transitional theory, describing better the movement of people, which is more based on mobility concept. It is a matter of time to see if this theory will be valuable in the future.

¹⁰ *The Stockholm Programme – An open and secure Europe serving and protecting citizens*, p. 27.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, p. 28.

Conclusions. Migration phenomenon in the European Union is a very complex issue. The European Union is both affected and afflicted by waves of immigrants, but it still cannot restrict entirely, because immigrants contribute to social, economic and cultural development of European societies.

The European Union is highly attractive for third-country nationals for several major reasons: peace, economic stability, respect of human rights and freedoms. It turns out that migration is a never-ending problem due to the European Union's objectives in the founding treaties, i.e. the numbers and the passions are not new. Consequently the European Union is extremely interested in developing its migration legislation which would regulate immigration processes in accordance with the changing priorities.

Recommendations. Why recommendations?; because traditional approaches towards migration issues do not fit properly the European Union as a whole. And it is worth taking into consideration recalibrating the European Union's place in the world.

Volens nolens there are a lot of actions to be undertaken in legislating, managing and performing research on migration phenomenon. It is desirable a rebooting of European migration policy by interconnecting it with foundation objectives of the European Union (effectiveness, efficiency); adapting to regional and global tendencies (high flexibility, immediate reactivity); harmonizing community and national regulations (one voice); promoting a permanent dialogue between the European Union and third countries (bi-lateral and multilateral cooperation); improving EU immigration system's capacity for responding differently to global challenges (up-to-date).

Challenges for research on migration refer to lack of systematic comparison, interdisciplinarity and integrating levels of analysis on migration in the European Union.

Potential research directions would face rethinking the relation between migration and settlement; shifting the focus from migrants to society; perspectives 'from outside'; specific thematic directions for future research (migration flows and their regulation; migration and development: causes and consequences; migrants' citizenship: legal status, rights and political participation; migrants' work, entrepreneurship and economic integration; social integration of immigrants with special reference to local and spatial dimensions; cultural, religious and linguistic diversity in Europe; identity, representation, interethnic relations and discrimination; time, generations and gender in migration and settlement; multilevel governance of migration). These levels and categories do neither have a limitative nor exhaustive character, because the process of globalization and rapid means of communication

require adapted or new methods and approaches of research on migration phenomenon in the European Union.

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